

Study of Cognitive Associated with Diabetes Induced by Alloxane Monohydrate in Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Introduction: Untreated diabetes can accelerate brain ageing and increase the risk of cognitive impairment and dementia. **Objective:** To assess the cognitive decline associated with alloxan monohydrate-induced diabetes in Wistar rats. **Material and methods:** This study involved 24 Wistar rats weighing between 150 and 300 g. They were divided into three groups: (1) normal rats, (2) untreated diabetic rats and (3) diabetic rats treated with D-erythrodihydrospingosine (inhibitors of SPK1 and SPK2). The rats were given glucose and food overnight to prevent hypoglycaemia. Behavioural experiments were carried out using object recognition and radial arm maze tests. **Results:** Behavioural analysis revealed significant differences in the time spent exploring familiar and novel objects in the rats. The study also assessed the cognitive impact of diabetes by evaluating spatial learning in an eight-branch radial maze. The results showed that diabetes affects working memory and that SPK1 and 2 inhibitors do not improve it in diabetic rats. **Conclusion** Our results show that diabetes induces an alteration in working memory and spatial learning difficulties.

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Introduction

Diabetes is a disease characterised by a genetic predisposition and acquired metabolic disorders that lead to a progressive decrease in insulin activity and secretion. Environmental factors such as changes in quality of life, overeating and a sedentary lifestyle can cause or accelerate these abnormalities. According to the WHO, the global prevalence of diabetes in adults aged 18 and over rose from 4.7% in 1980 to 8.5% in 2014. A study conducted in the Congo in 2004 found a prevalence of 7.6% in men aged 25 to 64 [1] It goes hand in hand with obesity, ageing and sedentary behaviour.

International epidemiological data on the prevalence of diabetes show major differences between developed and developing countries. Nevertheless, the incidence of diabetes is increasing in all countries. The International Diabetes Federation estimates that the number of people with diabetes will rise from 366 to 552 million by 2030 [2]. Hyperglycemia progresses unnoticed for years before a diagnosis is made. Its prevalence is not constantly updated. The costs associated with treating diabetes are a major and growing public health problem. The long-term effects of diabetes, with its micro- and macro-angiopathy complications, are debilitating diseases that require comprehensive patient management.

Today, numerous epidemiological, clinical and experimental arguments have accumulated to support the harmful effects of low-intensity inflammation in adipose tissue on the development of diabetes and numerous cognitive disorders. However, much recent research has highlighted that chronic diabetes in untreated patients leads to the formation of interneuronal amyloid plaques in the brain, resulting in neuro-pathological manifestations such as Alzheimer's disease (AD) [3]. Insulin resistance in type 2 diabetes, for example, has been shown to cause cognitive impairment [3] Despite these advances, effective treatment of chronic diabetes does not completely eliminate cognitive impairment [3,4]. The aim of our study was to evaluate the cognitive decline associated with alloxan monohydrate-induced diabetes in Wistar rats.

Equipment and Methods

Animal Rearing Conditions

Our study took place in the laboratory of the Marien Ngouabi Faculty of Health Sciences, within the experimental neuropathology unit. Twenty-four (24) male and female Wistar rats aged between seven and ten weeks, weighing between 150 and 300 g, had free access to food and water under standard laboratory conditions. The ethical standards of the Manual on the Treatment and Use of Experimental Animals were

followed [5]. Three groups were formed, each comprising eight Wistar rats:

- group 1: normal rats;
- group 2: untreated diabetic rats;
- Group 3: diabetic rats treated with D-erythrodihydrosphingosine (inhibitors of SPK1 and SPK2).

Induction of Diabetes

Injection of a single dose of 150 mg/kg body weight of alloxan monohydrate subcutaneously into fasted rats overnight [6] induced diabetes. Alloxan monohydrate was diluted in physiological water to a concentration of 0.05 g/ml. Rats were placed in cages. They were given free access to food and a 5% glucose solution to drink overnight to avoid hypoglycaemic shock [6-10].

Blood glucose measurement

Diabetes was confirmed three (03) days after alloxane injection by measuring blood glucose levels using a glucometer (called OnCall plus II). A drop of blood obtained through a small incision at the tip of the animal's tail was required to perform these fasting blood glucose measurements on days 1, 7, 14, 21 and 28. Rats with fasting blood glucose levels above 180 mg/dl were considered diabetic and were included in the experiment [11].

Determination of animal weight

The rats selected were weighed using an electronic balance from the first day before the onset of diabetes (start of the manipulation), and then on the different days (7, 14, 21 and 28).

Assessment of Cognitive Deficit

The behavioural experiments were carried out on schedule. Following induction of diabetes, two behavioural tests were used to assess cognitive decline.

Object recognition test

The test is based on the rodents' interest in exploring objects, particularly an unfamiliar object. It is used to assess short-term memory capacity [12]. The procedure is simple and is based on the natural exploration behaviour of rodents [13]. The test consists of three distinct stages: introduction to the context (familiarisation), acquisition and recall. Once they had become accustomed to the arena, the rats were treated and placed in the arena in the presence of two similar objects (training phase). Each object was recorded along with the time spent exploring it. During the test phase, the animals are confronted with a known object (discovered during the training phase) and an unknown object. According to [12], an animal with no memory problems will devote its time to exploring the new object.

- Familiarisation stage

Initially, the animal was placed in the device without any object and was free to explore the environment for 10 minutes. This step reduced the anxiety-provoking

aspect of the environment. The rat was then placed in its cage for 15 minutes.

- Acquisition stage

In the second stage, two identical objects were exposed to the animal. The rats were placed on opposite sides of the object in the apparatus and allowed to freely explore two identical objects for 10 min.

- Recall stage

After 24 hours, one of the two objects was replaced by a second. The animal was introduced into the device and allowed to explore both objects, the familiar and the new, for 10 minutes. Each animal was randomly alternated according to the type of object and its position (right or left). The choice of the new object was measured as the percentage of time spent exploring the new object in relation to the total time spent exploring the two objects. The time spent by the animal touching the object, sniffing it or being very close to it was treated as exploration. We then distinguished between the time spent on the familiar object (TF) and the time spent on the novel object (TN) as defined by Delacour and Ennaceur [12,14] and used by many authors [15-17].

Radial arm maze

The concept of the eight (8)-arm maze, developed by Olton and Samuelson (1976), is a widely used test for assessing memory and spatial information management abilities in various animal species. The labyrinth is made of wood and consists of a central area from which eight branches emerge, arranged like the spokes of a wheel. At the end of each branch, a pellet of food (45 mg) was placed and not replaced during the test, allowing a maximum of 8 rewards to be obtained. In fact, 24 rats divided into three groups of animals were tested in the maze. Firstly, the body weight of these animals was reduced to 85% of their initial values with the diet and this body weight was maintained

throughout the study. The animals were placed in the centre of the platform facing the same branch for each trial and for each rat (the maze branches were numbered from 1 to 8). The animal remained in the maze until it saw eight branches (four legs had to reach the entrance edge). The errors detected during the branch visits were recorded in chronological order. Each different group of animals was tested after each week, seven (07) days apart.

Collection of behavioural test parameters

We recorded each stage of the behavioural tests using a camera to better exploit the different parameters used as variables in each test.

Statistical Analysis

The mean of the data was expressed \pm SD. Comparisons between two groups were made using Student's *t*-tests. Results were examined using ANOVA for multiple comparisons. Figures and graphs were created using GraphPad Prism 5 software and were deemed to have a statistically significant P value <0.05.

Results

Body Weight of Wistar Rats

The weights of the rats in the various groups were recorded from D 1 to D 28.

A reduction in body weight was observed from day 7, with a significant difference assessed after statistical analysis using the Kruskal-Wallis test (P=0.027, n=8 per group). These results confirm the hypothesis that hyperglycaemia reduces physical weight (Figure 1).

Glycaemic Profile

Diabetes in rats was induced following administration of 150 mg/kg of alloxane monohydrate to group 2 (DTN) and group 3 (DTT) rats, which were complemented by SPK 1 and 2 inhibitors

Statistical analysis revealed a significant difference between groups 1 and groups 2 and 3 at D7 (P=0.0033, n=8 per group). The results indicate that rats in groups 2 and 3 have diabetes (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Body Weight of Three Different Groups of Wistar Rats

Note: Group 1 (GT) is made up of normal rats, group 2 (DTN) is made up of diabetic rats without a sphingosine kinase 1 and 2 inhibitor. Group 3 (DTT) was made up of diabetic rats with sphingosine kinase 1 and 2 inhibitors.

Figure 2: Average Blood Glucose Levels in the Three Different Groups of Wistar Rats

Behavioural Analysis

Object recognition test

The time taken by rats in group 1 (GT), group 2 (DTN) and group 3 (DTT) to explore a familiar object (OF) and a new object (ON) was measured on days 1, 7, 14, 21 and 28. The data revealed significant variations between OF and ON time on day 1 in all three groups ($p^{**}=0.0011$; $n=8$ for group 1 normal rats; $p^{**}=0.0019$; $n=8$ for group 2 diabetic rats and $p^{*}=0.027$; $n=8$ for

group 3 diabetic rats with SPK1 and SPK2 inhibitor). These significant differences were observed up to D21. However, at D28, we found no significant difference between OF and ON times in group 3 rats ($p=0.7018$; $n=8$). On the one hand, these results indicate that there is no memory impairment in the object recognition test in alloxane-induced diabetes, while on the other hand, inhibition of SPK1 and 2 could be responsible for the memory impairment observed.

Figure 3: Object Recognition Test on Days 1, 7, 14, 21 and 28 in Wistar Rats from Different Groups (GT, DTN and DTT)

Radial Arm Maze

To assess whether diabetes has an impact on cognitive ability, spatial learning was evaluated in an 8-arm radial maze. The animals were subjected to a working memory test in which, during each session, they had to traverse the eight arms of the radial maze. Returning to a previously visited arm was considered an error. In addition to the errors made, the number of correct visits to the arms in the first eight choices was also recorded. Statistical comparison using the ANOVA test revealed a significant difference between the group of normal rats and the group of rats with diabetes, which had or had not received an additional inhibitor of Sphingosine phosphate kinase 1 and 2 ($p=0.0029$; $n=8$ per group). This information indicates that diabetes affects working memory and that the Sphingosine kinase 1 and 2 inhibitor does not help to improve this memory in diabetic rats.

Figure 4: Spatial Learning

Note: Group 1 normal rats (GT) with group 2 (DTN) diabetic rats without sphingosine kinase inhibitor 1 and 2, and group 3 (DTT) diabetic rats with sphingosine kinase inhibitor 1 and 2 in a radial arm maze task. The mean number of errors for each session was taken into account.

Discussion

The aim of our study was to evaluate the cognitive decline associated with alloxan monohydrate-induced diabetes in Wistar rats. Following administration of alloxan monohydrate at a dose of 150 mg/kg, we observed an increase in blood glucose followed by a decrease in body weight. In addition, we used two behavioural tests to assess memory and learning capacity.

Assessment of Blood Glucose and Body Weight in Rats

Several studies have been published on animal models of diabetic rats [10,18-20] and have presented their benefits and disadvantages. In our research, we opted for the animal model using alloxane monohydrate. Our results are in line with those of other researchers [19,21] regarding the onset of hyperglycemia. Indeed, in our study, an increase in blood glucose was observed from the third day after administration of alloxan monohydrate at a dose of 150 mg/kg body weight ($P=0.0033$, $n=8$ per group) in rats in group 2 lacking SPK1 and SPK2 inhibitors and those in group 3 with SPK1 and SPK2 inhibitors. Alloxane diabetes is a dangerous variant of insulin-deprivation diabetes known as alloxane diabetes [22]. Alloxane causes diabetes in animals by destroying insulin-producing beta cells in the pancreas; it inhibits thiol-dependent enzymes such as glucokinase and hexokinase [23]. The presence of alloxane leads to the creation of reactive oxygen species such as superoxide radicals, hydrogen peroxide and hydroxyl radicals [24]. These data confirm that alloxane causes hyperglycaemia by destroying pancreatic islet beta cells, leading to a significant decrease in insulin release. We then gradually assessed the weight of the rats in the various groups in our study, from D 1 to D 28.

We obtained results similar to those of other authors [6,25,26] on the reduction in body weight in rats made diabetic by alloxane. On day 7, we observed a reduction in body weight in diabetic rats in group 2 and group 3, without and with SPK1 and SPK2 inhibitors respectively, compared with normal rats in group 1, with a significant difference ($P=0.027$, $n=8$ per group). In general, the reduction in body weight in diabetes mellitus is due to the stimulation of gluconeogenesis production. Indeed, an acceleration in the process of protein and fat degradation leads to a significant reduction in body weight, resulting in increased muscle atrophy and tissue protein loss [20]. This information confirms that hyperglycemia leads to a reduction in body weight. Other researchers such as [27]; [28]; [29]; [30]; [31]; [32] have also reported a significant decrease in body weight caused by streptozotocin-induced diabetes compared to normal subjects. Similarly, [33] also obtained similar results and suggest that body weight loss can be attributed to the lipolytic effects of glucocorticoids on adipose tissue. In addition to

accelerating lipolysis, glucocorticoids promote proteolysis and stimulate gluconeogenesis. These metabolic effects are probably linked to the lack of insulin, a lipogenic hormone. At the same time, these results resemble metabolic dysfunctions observed in patients suffering from Alzheimer's disease, whether diabetic or not. Weight loss, already mentioned by Alois Alzheimer, is seen as a clinical manifestation of the disease, affecting between 20% and 45% of patients. It is linked to a rapid progression of the disease, greater institutionalisation and increased mortality.

Assessment of Cognitive Abilities in Rats

Rodents need a highly developed memory to survive in the wild, as they need to learn and remember their spatial environment. Memory tests are used to assess the acquisition of a spatial environment, such as the aquatic and radial maze tests. Several other tests are used to identify spatial learning: object recognition, the T maze (54), the Barnes maze (14), and non-spatial learning: fear conditioning test (4), avoidance experiments (144). In our study, two main tests were used, namely: Object recognition and the eight (08) branch radial maze.

The object recognition test was used to study the short-term memory of diabetic rats induced by alloxane monohydrate [13]. Although the anatomical basis of the processes underlying object recognition memory is not yet known, some studies have already defined the importance of the hippocampus in recognition and familiarity processes [34-36]. Various techniques have been used to study the role of the hippocampus in the object recognition test [37]. In our study, we calculated the time required for rats in different groups to explore the familiar object (OF) and the new object (ON) at D1, D7, D14, D21 and D28 ($n=8$ per group) with a 24 h delay between the acquisition phase and the recall phase. The results of our study revealed significant differences between OF and ON time from day 1 to D21 for the three (03) groups of rats (respectively, $p^{**}=0.0011$; $n=8$ for group 1 of normal rats; $p^{**}=0.0019$; $n=8$ for group 2 of diabetic rats and $p^*=0.027$; $n=8$ for group 3 of diabetic rats with SPK1 and SPK2 inhibitor). On the other hand, at D28, we found no significant disparity between OF and ON times in group 3 rats ($p=0.701$). Using this test involving the hippocampus, it can be concluded that not only is there no impairment of memory in the hippocampus of alloxan-induced diabetic rats, but hyperglycemia could also inhibit S1P expression. Furthermore, inhibition of SPK1 and SPK2 could be responsible for the memory alterations observed in alloxan-induced diabetes. Similar to our results, rats with hippocampal lesions have been shown to be unable to recognise objects at 10 minutes, 1 hour and 24 hours [38]. However, rodents with deficits in this test have already shown beneficial effects of polyphenols on object recognition. According to [39],

proanthocyanidins, polyphenols, have the ability to restore object recognition memory capacity in a mouse model of accelerated senescence (SAMP8) that suffers from memory problems. Administration of curcumin made it easier for elderly mice to recognise a new object [40].

The 8-arm maze test was used in our study to assess short- and long-term spatial working memory in rodents [41]. Animals were tested on task working memory, where they were required to visit each arm of the radial maze only once chronologically during each session. Each time an empty arm was visited, and therefore already visited, was perceived as an error. In addition to the number of errors made, the number of correct arm visits in the first eight choices was also recorded. A significant variation ($p=0.0029$; $n=8$ per group) was found between the group of normal rats and the group of diabetic rats that received an SPK1 and SPK2 inhibitor in addition or not. These data suggest that diabetes modifies working memory and that the Sphingosine kinase 1 and 2 inhibitor does not restore this memory in rats with diabetes. In addition to these results, it has been shown that Zucker fa/fa rats (which have a mutation in the leptin receptor) are hyperphagic, dyslipidaemic, obese and have hyperinsulinism associated with glucose intolerance. Eight months after the onset of diabetes, they showed impaired memory in the Morris water maze test, long-term potentiation and neuronal loss in the CA1 hippocampal region [42]. Numerous studies have also validated these results by observing age-related cognitive deficits in various tasks used to assess the Rat's spatial memory [43]. These include the tasks performed in the Morris water maze. According to these authors, it has been shown that the reduced memory capacity of rats in spatial memorisation and learning tasks is caused by an alteration in synaptic connections [44], due to a reduction in neuronal plasticity [43,44]. In mice, other studies have also highlighted deficiencies in working memory. To illustrate the integrity of spatial working memory in a spontaneous alternation task, mice aged mice aged eighteen to nineteen (18-19) months performed less well than their younger counterparts aged four to five (4-5) months [45].

Hyperglycémie and Cognitive Decline

Previous research has shown a correlation between poorly controlled hyperglycemia and memory [46,47]. According to [48], chronic hyperglycemia is linked to insulin resistance (IR), which also affects certain parts of the brain. It causes a reduction in autophosphorylation of the insulin receptor and activates the expression of protein kinase C, a protein that dephosphorylates the insulin receptor. According to [49], insulin receptors (IR) have been identified in the hippocampus and medial temporal cortex, which partly

explains the memory problems. Problems with LTP (long-term potentiation) and spatial memory have been observed in mice with reduced IR expression in the hippocampus [50]. In our study, we found impaired working memory in diabetic rats and impaired exploratory behaviour during spatial learning ($p=0.0029$; $n=8$ per group) due to the number of errors made during open arm entry visits observed in the eight (08) branch radial maze test. In line with our results, it has been shown that type 1 diabetes is frequently associated with a decrease in reasoning speed and mental flexibility [51], that type 2 diabetes also affects learning and memory [52] and that cognitive decline during a 7-year follow-up is more marked in diabetic patients, particularly older ones [53]. A correlation between diabetes and dementia is common [54]. Elderly insulin-powered diabetic rats show weaker hippocampal synaptic plasticity than younger rats. Similarly, it appears that the duration of diabetes has an impact on its repercussions; in insulin-privileged rats, prolonged hyperglycemia has an impact on hippocampal neurons. The negative effects of hypoglycemia are also present. A week later, diabetic rats were euthanised after being treated with high doses of insulin or saline. Rats suffering from hypoglycemia showed a more significant reduction in neuronal capacity in the hippocampus [4].

Conclusion

Our study of cognitive disorders revealed behavioral disturbances in the evaluation of cognitive functions in alloxane monohydrate-induced diabetic rats. In diabetic rats, we found impaired working memory and impaired exploratory behaviour during spatial learning. In the absence of data to prevent cognitive impairment, our results could help to better understand the link between cognitive decline and hyperglycemia. Thus, highlighting the importance of comprehensive management of diabetic patients with neurocognitive disorders and preventing vascular complications of diabetes. It is therefore necessary to improve glycemic control, while ensuring optimum control of all associated vascular risk factors.

References

- [1] Kimbally-Kaky G. Hypertension artérielle et autres facteurs de risque cardiovasculaire à Brazzaville. Ministère de la Santé et de la Population — OMS. Rapport d'enquête. Brazzaville; 2004. Available from: http://www.who.int/entity/chp/steps/STEPS_Congo_Data.pdf.
- [2] International Diabetes Federation. IDF Diabetes Atlas. 6th ed. Brussels: IDF; 2013. Available from: <http://www.diabetesatlas.org/>.
- [3] Maceyka M, Harikumar KB, Milstien S, Spiegel S. Sphingosine-1-phosphate signaling and its role in

disease. Trends Cell Biol. 2012;22(1):50–60. doi: 10.1016/j.tcb.2011.09.003.

[4] Biessels GJ, Staekenborg S, Brunner E, Brayne C, Scheltens P. Risk of dementia in diabetes mellitus: a systematic review. Lancet Neurol. 2006;5(1):64-74. doi:10.1016/S1474-4422(05)70284-2.

[5] Conseil Canadien de Protection des Animaux. Manuel sur le soin et l'utilisation des animaux d'expérimentation. Vol. 2. Ottawa, Ont.: CCPA; 1984.

[6] Auroba N, Nibras. Study Antidiabetic Effect of Momordica Charantia (bittergourd) seeds on Alloxan Induced Diabetic Rats. Iraqi J Vet Med. 2010;34(1):1-10.

[7] Pribac G, Craciun C, Szoke-Nagy T, et al. Comparative ultrastructural study of pancreatic beta cells from diabetic rats treated with fenugreek seed flour or Ganoderma. Ann RSCB. 2011;16(1):62–80.

[8] Rajeshkannan V, Stalinrajasekar G, Rajesh P, et al. Antidiabetic activity on ethanolic extracts of fruits of Terminalia chebula Retz. Am J Drug Discov Dev. 2012;2(3):135–142. doi: 10.3923/ajdd.2012.135.142.

[9] Daisy P, Rajathi KS. Antihyperglycemic and antihyperlipidemic effects of Clitoria ternatea Linn. in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. Afr J Microbiol Res. 2009;3(5):287-91.

[10] Tiwari BK, Kumar D, Abidi AB, Rizvi SI. Efficacy of composite extract from leaves and fruits of medicinal plants used in traditional diabetic therapy against oxidative stress in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. ISRN Pharmacol. 2014;2014:1-7. doi: 10.1155/2014/608590.

[11] El Baky HHA, El Rahman AAA, Mekawia EM, Ibrahim EA, Shalapy NM. The antidiabetic and anti-lipidemic effects of *Peganum harmala* seeds in diabetic rats. Der Pharmacia Lettre. 2016;8(1):1-10.

[12] Ennaceur A, Meliani K. A new one-trial test for neurobiological studies of memory in rats. III: Spatial vs. non-spatial working memory. Behav Brain Res. 1992;51(1):83-92. doi: 10.1016/s0166-4328(05)80315-8.

[13] Bevins RA, Besheer J. Object recognition in rats and mice: a one-trial non-matching-to-sample learning task to study 'recognition memory'. Nat Protoc. 2006;1(3):1306-11. doi:10.1038/nprot.2006.205.

[14] Ennaceur A, Delacour J. A new one-trial test for neurobiological studies of memory in rats. I: Behavioral data. Behav Brain Res. 1988;31(1):47-59. doi: 10.1016/0166-4328(88)90157-x.

[15] Davis WM, Smith SG. Conditioned reinforcement as a measure of the rewarding properties of drugs. In: Bozarth MA, editor. Methods of assessing the reinforcing properties of abused drugs. New York: Springer; 1987. p. 199-210.

[16] Mogensen J, Christensen LH, Johansson A, et al. Place learning in scopolamine-treated rats: the roles of distal cues and catecholaminergic mediation. Neurobiol Learn Mem. 2002;78(1):139–156. doi: 10.1006/nlme.2001.4041.

[17] Pitsikas N, Rigamonti AE, Cella S, et al. The non-NMDA receptor antagonist NBQX does not affect rats' performance in the object recognition task. Pharmacol Res. 2002;45(1):43–46. doi: 10.1006/phrs.2001.0900.

[18] Karthik D, Vijayakumar R, Pazhanichamy K, Ravikumar S. A proteomics approach to identify the differential protein level in cardiac muscle of diabetic rat. Biomed Pharmacother. 2014;61:1-9. doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2014.07.001.

[19] Djomeni PDD, Tédong L, Asongalem EA, Dimo T, Sokeng SD, Kamtchouing P. Hypoglycaemic and antidiabetic effect of root extracts of *Ceiba pentandra* in normal and diabetic rats. Afr J Tradit Complement Altern Med. 2006;3(1):129-136. doi: 10.4314/ajtcam.v3i1.31147.

[20] Daisy P, Feril G, Kani J. Evaluation of antidiabetic activity of various extracts of *Cassia auriculata* Linn. bark on streptozotocin induced diabetic Wistar rats. Int J Pharm Pharm Sci. 2012;4(4):312-8.

[21] Loubano-Voumbi G, Diaw M, Ouedraogo V, et al. Characteristics of animal model of painful diabetic neuropathy induced by alloxan in subcutaneously in rats. J Glob Biosci. 2015;4(6):2478-2485.

[22] Ladouri A, Harkouk Y. Effet du décocté de *Zygophyllum album* Coss sur le diabète et le stress oxydant associé [dissertation]. Université d'Alger; 2012.

[23] Jorns A, Munday R, Tiedge M, Lenzen S. Comparative toxicity of alloxan, N-alkylalloxans and ninhydrin to isolated pancreatic islets in vitro. J Endocrinol. 1997;155(2):283-293. doi: 10.1677/joe.0.1550283.

[24] Duncan M, Matheka A, Kitua M, Faraj A, Alkizim OA. Peculiar glycemic patterns in alloxan-induced diabetes animal model. Afr J Pharmacol Ther. 2012;1(1):30-34.

[25] Chaudhry J, Ghosh N, Roy K, Chandra R. Antihyperglycemic effect of a new thiazolidinedione analogue and its role in ameliorating oxidative stress in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. Life Sci. 2007;80(12):1135-42. doi:10.1016/j.lfs.2006.12.027.

[26] Reyes BA, Bautista ND, Tanquilut NC, et al. Anti-diabetic potentials of *Momordica charantia* and *Andrographis paniculata* and their effects on estrous cyclicity of alloxan-induced diabetic rats. J Ethnopharmacol. 2006;105(1-2):196–200. doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2005.10.020.

- [27] Hajzadeh M, Rajaei Z, Ghamami G, Tamiz A. The effect of *Salvia officinalis* leaf extract on blood glucose in streptozotocin-diabetic rats. *Pharmacologyonline*. 2011;1:213–220.
- [28] Kanter M. Protective effects of thymoquinone on β -cell damage in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Tip Arařtırmaları Dergisi*. 2009;7(2):64-70.
- [29] Asad M, Aslam M, Munir TA, Nadeem A. Effect of *Acacia nilotica* leaves extract on hyperglycaemia, lipid profile and platelet aggregation in streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*. 2011;23(2):3-7.
- [30] Luke UO, Ebong PE, Eyong EU, Robert AE, Ufot SU, Egbung GE. Effect of ethanolic root and twig extracts of *Vernonia amygdalina* (ETIDOT) on liver function parameters of streptozotocin-induced hyperglycemic and normal Wistar rats. *Eur Sci J*. 2013;9(30):199–211.
- [31] Saini S, Sharma S. Antidiabetic effect of *Helianthus annuus* L. seeds ethanolic extract in streptozotocin-nicotinamide induced type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2013;5(2):382–387.
- [32] Kaur G, Kamboj P, Kalia AN. Antidiabetic and anti-hypercholesterolemic effects of aerial parts of *Sida cordifolia* Linn. on streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Indian J Nat Prod Resour*. 2011;2(4):428-434.
- [33] Omari N, Dahmani-Ait Akli Y, Labrousse F, Hadj Bekkouche F. Influence de la streptozotocine sur l'axe corticotrope du rat Wistar (*Rattus norvegicus*). *Bull Soc R Sci Liège*. 2011;80:907–938.
- [34] Mumby DG. Perspectives on object-recognition memory following hippocampal damage: lessons from studies in rats. *Behav Brain Res*. 2001;127(1-2):159–181. doi: 10.1016/s0166-4328(01)00367-9.
- [35] Rossato JI, Bevilaqua LR, Myskiw JC, et al. On the role of hippocampal protein synthesis in the consolidation and reconsolidation of object recognition memory. *Learn Mem*. 2007;14(1):36–46. doi: 10.1101/lm.422607.
- [36] Squire LR, Wixted JT, Clark RE. Recognition memory and the medial temporal lobe: a new perspective. *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2007;8(11):872–883. doi: 10.1038/nrn2154.
- [37] Dere E, Huston JP, De Souza Silva MA. The pharmacology, neuroanatomy and neurogenetics of one-trial object recognition in rodents. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev*. 2007;31(5):673-704. doi:10.1016/j.neubiorev.2007.01.005.
- [38] Clark RE, Zola SM, Squire LR. Impaired recognition memory in rats after damage to the hippocampus. *J Neurosci*. 2000;20(23):8853-60. doi:10.1523/JNEUROSCI.20-23-08853.2000.
- [39] Yokozawa T, Kim HY, Kim HJ, Okubo T, Chu DC, Juneja LR. Anti-aging effects of oligomeric proanthocyanidins isolated from persimmon fruits. *Drug Discov Ther*. 2007;1(2):123–133.
- [40] Yu SY, Zhang M, Luo J, et al. Curcumin ameliorates memory deficits via neuronal nitric oxide synthase in aged mice. *Prog Neuropsychopharmacol Biol Psychiatry*. 2013;45:47–53. doi: 10.1016/j.pnpbp.2013.04.006.
- [41] Hodges H. Maze procedures: the radial-arm and water maze compared. *Brain Res Cogn Brain Res*. 1996;3(3-4):167-181. doi: 10.1016/0926-6410(96)00004-3.
- [42] Biessels GJ, Gispen WH. The impact of diabetes on cognition: what can be learned from rodent models? *Neurobiol Aging*. 2005;26 Suppl 1:36-41. doi:10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2005.08.014.
- [43] Rosenzweig ES, Barnes CA. Impact of aging on hippocampal function: plasticity, network dynamics, and cognition. *Prog Neurobiol*. 2003;69(3):143–179. doi: 10.1016/s0301-0082(02)00126-0.
- [44] Kennard JA, Woodruff-Pak DS. Age sensitivity of behavioral tests and brain substrates of normal aging in mice. *Front Aging Neurosci*. 2011;3:9. doi: 10.3389/fnagi.2011.00009.
- [45] Vandesquille M, Krazem A, Louis C, et al. S 18986 reverses spatial working memory impairments in aged mice: comparison with memantine. *Psychopharmacology (Berl)*. 2011;215(4):709–720. doi: 10.1007/s00213-011-2165-1.
- [46] Bruel-Jungerman E, Rampon C, Laroche S. Adult hippocampal neurogenesis, synaptic plasticity and memory: facts and hypotheses. *Rev Neurosci*. 2007;18(2):93-114. doi:10.1515/REVNEURO.2007.18.2.93.
- [47] Arendt T. Synaptic degeneration in Alzheimer's disease. *Acta Neuropathol*. 2009 Jul;118(1):167-79. doi:10.1007/s00401-009-0483-9.
- [48] Medjdoub H. Contribution à la recherche d'éventuelles activités biologiques de *Zygophyllum geslini* Coss. Université de Tlemcen; 2013.
- [49] Craft S. The role of metabolic disorders in Alzheimer's disease and vascular dementia: two roads converged? *Arch Neurol*. 2009 Mar;66(3):300-5. doi:10.1001/archneurol.2009.27.
- [50] Grillo CA, Piroli GG, Lawrence RC, et al. Hippocampal insulin resistance impairs spatial learning and synaptic plasticity. *Diabetes*. 2015;64(11):3927-3936. doi: 10.2337/db15-0596.

- [51] Brands AM, Biessels GJ, de Haan EH, Kappelle LJ, Kessels RP. The effects of type 1 diabetes on cognitive performance: a meta-analysis. *Diabetes Care*. 2005;28(3):726-35. doi:10.2337/diacare.28.3.726.
- [52] Awad N, Gagnon M, Messier C. The relationship between impaired glucose tolerance, type 2 diabetes, and cognitive function. *J Clin Exp Neuropsychol*. 2004;26(8):1044-80. doi:10.1080/13803390490514875.
- [53] Allen KV, Frier BM, Strachan MW. The relationship between type 2 diabetes and cognitive dysfunction: longitudinal studies and their methodological limitations. *Eur J Pharmacol*. 2004;490(1-3):169-75. doi:10.1016/j.ejphar.2004.02.054.
- [54] Duron E, Hanon O. Vascular risk factors, cognitive decline, and dementia. *Vasc Health Risk Manag*. 2008;4(2):363-381. doi: 10.2147/vhrm.s1807.
- [55] Guérin O, Andrieu S, Schneider SM, et al. Different modes of weight loss in Alzheimer's disease: a prospective study of 395 patients. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2005;82(2):435-441. doi: 10.1093/ajcn.82.2.435.
- [56] Kimbally-Kaky G. Hypertension artérielle et autres facteurs de risque cardiovasculaire à Brazzaville. Ministère de la Santé et de la Population — OMS. Rapport d'enquête. Brazzaville; 2004. Available from: http://www.who.int/entity/chp/steps/STEPS_Congo_Data.pdf.
- [57] Raja NL, Sundaranathavalli S, Ananthi JJ, Nirmaladevi J, Kumarappan C, Kumaraguruparan P, Yaseen KA. Antihyperglycaemic activity of aqueous extract of *Vinca rosea* Linn. in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. *Pharmacologyonline*. 2008;3:354-362.
- [58] Olton DS, Samuelson RJ. Remembrance of places past: spatial memory in rats. *J Exp Psychol Anim Behav Process*. 1976;2(2):97-116. doi: 10.1037/0097-7403.2.2.97.

